

Mapping physiology: a systems biology approach for the development of alternative methods in toxicology

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Summary

Chemical safety assessment still heavily relies on animal testing, presenting ethical dilemmas and limited human predictive value. New approach methodologies (NAMs), including *in vitro* and *in silico* techniques, offer alternative solutions. *In silico* toxicology has made progress in predicting chemical effects but frequently lacks biological mechanistic foundations. Recent developments focus on mechanistic understanding of adverse effects inflicted by chemicals, as embedded in (quantitative) adverse outcome pathways (AOPs). However, there is a demand for more detailed mechanistic insights at the gene and cell levels, encompassing both pathology and physiology. Drawing inspiration from the Disease Maps Project, this paper introduces Physiological Maps (PMs) as comprehensive graphical representations of biochemical processes related to specific organ functions. PMs are standardized using Systems Biology Graphical Notation and controlled vocabularies and annotations. Curation guidelines have been developed to ensure reproducibility and usability. This paper presents the methodology used to build PMs, emphasizing the essential collaboration between domain experts and curators. PMs offer user-friendly, standardized visualization for data analysis and educational purposes. Enabling a better understanding of (patho)physiology, they also complement and support the development of AOPs by providing detailed mechanistic information at the gene and cell level. Furthermore, PMs contribute to developing *in vitro* test batteries and to building (dynamic) *in silico* models aiming to predict the toxicity of chemicals. Collaborative efforts between the toxicology and systems biology communities are crucial for creating standardized and comprehensive PMs, supporting and accelerating the development of human-relevant NAMs for next-generation risk assessment.

48 **Keywords**

49 physiological map, standardized graphical representation, curated biochemical networks,
50 conceptual *in silico* models, new approach methodology.

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55 **1. Introduction**

56 Currently, the **safety assessment of chemicals** heavily relies on animal testing, which raises
57 serious ethical concerns and is poorly predictive of human safety, as the effects observed in
58 animals may not necessarily reflect the responses seen in humans (Vinken et al., 2021).
59 Consequently, there is a pressing need for alternative methods to reduce animal testing and
60 improve chemical risk assessment. **New approach methodologies (NAMs)** include *in vitro*
61 (experimental) approaches, *in silico* (computational) approaches and combinations thereof. In
62 terms of ***in silico* toxicology**, a great deal of effort has gone into developing methods for
63 predicting the activity of a chemical in the body based on its structural properties (e.g., read-
64 across, QSAR models) (Luechtefeld and Hartung, 2017; Luechtefeld et al., 2018; Punt et al.,
65 2020; Schmeisser et al., 2023). However, these predictive models are not based on a solid
66 mechanistic foundation using knowledge of biological processes (Wittwehr et al., 2017).

67
68 Nowadays, the focus of (*in silico*) toxicology has shifted from simply determining a compound's
69 hazard to providing a mechanistic explanation, particularly with the development of **adverse**
70 **outcome pathways (AOPs)** (Hemmerich and Ecker, 2020; Schmeisser et al., 2023). An AOP
71 is an analytical construct capturing existing knowledge and describing a sequential chain of
72 causally linked events at different levels of biological organization (e.g., cell, tissue, organ)
73 that lead to an adverse health effect in an organism following exposure to a stressor ¹ (Ankley
74 et al., 2010). AOPs, therefore, bring some mechanistic explanation to allow for interpretation
75 of hazards and to support chemical risk assessment. Recent years have seen the
76 development of quantitative AOPs (qAOPs), from simple dose–response modeling to more
77 complicated Bayesian network modeling and differential equation based systems biology
78 approaches (Ito et al., 2024). Although AOPs and qAOPs are able to provide more mechanistic
79 information, chemical risk assessment would benefit from: (1) a more detailed representation
80 of biological mechanisms at the gene and cell levels, (2) a description of these mechanisms
81 not only in the context of the pathology/adverse outcome but for the underlying physiology in
82 general.

83
84 In recent years, the Disease Maps Project Community has brought the concept of **disease**
85 **maps (DM)** to the forefront, building a bridge between the domains of biological and
86 computational research (Ostaszewski et al., 2019). By fostering the development of DMs, this
87 open community effort aims to graphically and comprehensively represent biological
88 mechanisms, such as interconnected signaling, metabolic and gene regulatory pathways, in

¹ OECD website: <https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/sub-issues/testing-of-chemicals/adverse-outcome-pathways.html>
, accessed August 19, 2024

89 standardized and machine-readable formats for various human disorders. While several
90 projects are currently mapping a wide range of diseases, a similar effort has not been made
91 to map the undisturbed underlying physiology. Drawing inspiration from the DM project, we
92 believe that **physiological maps** (PMs), *i.e.* mapping the physiology of specific biological
93 processes, can be a cornerstone for the development and refinement of alternative methods
94 in toxicology, including *in vitro* test batteries, AOPs and *in silico* predictive models.
95

96 **2. Physiological maps: concept and methodology**

97 By integrating biological knowledge from existing databases and scientific literature, the PMs
98 developed as part of the European Commission funded Horizon 2020 ONTOX project² can be
99 described as graphical representations of cellular and molecular processes associated with
100 specific organ functions (Vinken et al., 2021). They encapsulate comprehensive physiological
101 knowledge in a standardized graphical notation that is designed for human comprehension
102 and is also machine readable. In ONTOX, organ-specific PMs are currently being developed:
103 bile secretion and lipid metabolism (liver), nephron physiology (kidney), neural tube closure
104 (updated version of Heusinkveld et al., 2021), and cognitive function development (brain).

105 **Main workflow**

106 The workflow used to build and exploit PMs in ONTOX (Figure 1) is strongly inspired by that
107 of the DM Project and comprises 4 main phases: (1) planning, (2) curation, (3) updating, and
108 (4) application (Mazein, Acencio, et al., 2023). During the **planning phase**, domain experts
109 and curators define the purpose and scope of the PM, identify the biological mechanisms to
110 be mapped, determine granularity (e.g., the architecture of the map, including the presence of
111 submaps, and the level of details for representing the molecular interactions) and list the key
112 components in terms of cell types, molecules and pathways. The **curation phase** involves
113 retrieving available knowledge and data from literature and databases, which are then
114 integrated into a PM using CellDesigner, a structured diagram editor (Funahashi et al., 2008).
115 For the **updating phase**, the PM is uploaded to the Molecular Interaction Networks
116 Visualization (MINERVA) platform, a navigable tool (Hoksza et al., 2020), enabling better
117 visualization and facilitating feedback from domain experts. In the **application phase**, PMs
118 can be exploited in many possible ways, such as (omics) data visualization, benchmarking
119 and filling gaps in AOPs, identifying new *in vitro* assays, exploring drug targets and developing
120 *in silico* models.

121 **Human resources: domain experts, curators, data scientists**

122 Every phase of this workflow requires strong collaboration between curators and domain
123 experts who are identified in the planning phase. While curators drive PM development
124 (design, documentation, curation, visualization, updates and user support), domain experts
125 also play key roles throughout the process by: (i) helping to define the goals and scope of the
126 PM, particularly in terms of the applications required; (ii) identifying the relevant pathways and
127 hallmarks to be mapped; (iii) screening different data resources and providing relevant
128 knowledge to be integrated; (iv) providing continuous feedback for updating the maps; and (v)
129 guiding the application phase.
130

² ONTOX website : <https://ontox-project.eu/>

131
132 **Figure 1. Workflow to construct ONTOX physiological maps.** The workflow consists of 4 main phases: (1)
133 Planning, (2) Curation, (3) Update and (4) Application. Inspired by Mazein, Acencio, *et al.*, 2023.

134

135 **Data resources**

136 The knowledge integrated in the PMs comes from various sources including original research
137 papers, review articles and books covering the physiology of the processes concerned. In
138 addition, the following databases and platforms are used: WikiPathways (Agrawal *et al.*, 2024),
139 Reactome (Gillespie *et al.*, 2022), Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG)
140 (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2023), among other pathway resources. Parts of maps and/or submaps from
141 other DM projects are adapted and integrated in the PMs (Fujita *et al.*, 2014; Mazein *et al.*,
142 2018; Ostaszewski *et al.*, 2019, 2021; Serhan *et al.*, 2020). Manual data extraction is
143 complemented by AI-based tools, using natural language processing in particular, to integrate
144 human-readable data into semi-automated data extraction projects (Bozada *et al.*, 2021;
145 Corradi *et al.*, 2022). The ONTOX project aims to further automate the process from data
146 extraction to graphical representation by integrating tools for data extraction, data conversion
147 and diagram editing.

148 **Graphical standard**

149 The **Systems Biology Graphical Notation** (SBGN) is a visual language used to represent
150 biochemical interaction networks in a standardized and unambiguous way (Novère *et al.*,
151 2009). This language has been developed by a community including biologists, biochemists,
152 mathematicians, and computer scientists, with the aim of standardizing the graphical notation
153 used in maps of biological processes (such as gene regulation, metabolism and cell signaling).
154 PMs are designed to comply as closely as possible with SBGN, in particular the Process
155 Description (PD) language, one of the three SBGN languages. PD depicts how entities,
156 represented by nodes in the network, change from one form to another and influence each
157 other (mechanistic, directed and sequential descriptions) (Mazein *et al.*, 2018; Rougny *et al.*,

158 2019). In some modules, such as gene regulatory networks, the SBGN Activity Flow language
159 is used as a method to prevent visual overload on the map. This approach ensures a clean
160 design that remains adaptable for modeling purposes and that can be detailed in the PD
161 language on request.

162 **Editor and visualization software**

163 PMs have been drawn based on SBGN using the **CellDesigner** structured diagram editor
164 (Funahashi et al., 2008). CellDesigner is used to graphically represent SBGN-compatible
165 networks, storing the maps in the **Systems Biology Markup Language** (SBML), a free and
166 open software data format for describing models in systems biology (Keating et al., 2020).
167 CellDesigner does not fully comply with SBGN (e.g. for the shape of the nodes), but we have
168 ensured that the representation of the network is as close as possible to the standard. PMs
169 can then be imported onto the MINERVA platform, enabling annotation, data cross-linking and
170 improved visualization (Gawron et al., 2016). **MINERVA** integrates automated tools which
171 annotate nodes in the PMs using the name of an element (e.g. HGNC approved symbol) or
172 its MIRIAM identifier such as ChEBI, Ensembl, Uniprot and Gene Ontology. MINERVA also
173 enables an interactive visualization for both elements and interactions, provides functionalities
174 for content exploration (such as searching for drug targets), allows for the overlay of
175 experimental datasets and facilitates feedback from reviewers. Altogether, the
176 CellDesigner/MINERVA platform offers: (i) the ability to draw biochemical networks, integrate
177 and annotate data from a variety of sources; (ii) easy-to-interpret visual representation; and
178 (iii) compatibility with other platforms and machine readability, allowing for sharing data and
179 building *in silico* models. Figure 2 shows a submap of the liver metabolism PM (hepatocyte-
180 specific cholesterol metabolism) as designed on CellDesigner.

181 **Sustainability**

182 PMs are developed on the basis of current knowledge and are intended to be continuously
183 updated as new data becomes available. The possibility to have a **modular structure**
184 (dividing the main map into submaps) offered by the CellDesigner/MINERVA platform
185 facilitates complex data visualization and thereby strongly simplifies the review and curation
186 processes. Smaller modules can then be submitted to WikiPathways (Pico et al., 2008;
187 Agrawal et al., 2024) to accelerate curation via a community effort. To ensure the
188 development, curation and update of maps that adhere to the FAIR principles (Findability,
189 Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) (Wilkinson et al., 2016), we developed **curation**
190 **guidelines** for PMs, providing recommendations in terms of design, annotation,
191 documentation (e.g., planning document, issue report), quality control, and storage (Ladeira
192 et al., 2024). These guidelines are expected to enhance scientific reproducibility, facilitate the
193 usage of the maps and the development of new modules. When PMs are ready for publication,
194 they can be made publicly available online on MINERVA, which is a stable infrastructure
195 hosted by ELIXIR Luxembourg³. As PMs require **continuous updating**, review and feedback
196 from domain experts and curators will continue after publication. In terms of traceability,
197 successive versions of PMs are stored in the BioStudies database (part of the ELIXIR
198 infrastructure) and can be tracked by persistent identifiers, while all associated data and
199 metadata are stored on GitHub⁴.

³ <https://elixir-luxembourg.org/services/catalog/minerva>

⁴ <https://github.com/ontox-maps>

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Figure 2. Example of a PM. Hepatocyte-specific cholesterol metabolism submap designed on CellDesigner, and accessible through MINERVA.

204 3. Applications

205 The workflow used to build PMs is largely inspired by the DM Project, using a diagram editor
206 (CellDesigner) to develop and store maps in SBML and a user-friendly platform for annotation
207 and visualization (MINERVA). Unlike DMs, the foundation of PMs is, as their name suggests,
208 the unperturbed physiology of the mechanisms involved. We believe that the mapping of
209 physiology is highly complementary to the representation of disease mechanisms, enabling a
210 better understanding of both physiological and pathological processes, improvements in target
211 identification and the personalization of therapies. In addition, PM-derived applications should
212 benefit from the existing pipelines developed for successful DM applications (Highlight Box).

213 Assessment of AOPs

214 Not only are PMs complementary to DMs, but they can also be seen as a supporting tool for
215 developing AOPs. In addition to the mechanistic information contained in AOPs, PMs add
216 another level of detail in terms of gene regulation, biochemical networks and cell-cell
217 interactions. As a benchmarking tool, PMs can help fill gaps in AOPs, identify new key events

218 and molecular initiating events, and build more comprehensive AOP networks. Recently, the
219 SBGN-based approach used for building PMs and DMs has been applied to transform an AOP
220 into a standardized, structured digital diagram, using controlled vocabulary and automated
221 annotations (Mazein, Shoaib, et al., 2023; Mazein et al., 2024). This paves the way for the
222 integration of PMs and AOPs in a multi-layer structure, linking data from one layer to another.

223

Building on the success of disease maps

- The **Parkinson's DM** was the first map published in the context of the DM Project. It resulted from the manual curation of more than 1000 research articles and public databases from which the information was integrated in a molecular interaction map.
- The **Atlas of Cancer Signalling Network (ACSN)** has been successfully exploited. Applications: (1) an example is the analysis of omics data from breast cancer cell lines using the ACSN identified different molecular portraits of sensitivity to Dbait and PARP inhibitors and therefore explained the synergistic therapeutic effect of these two drugs; (2) from the several applications of ACSN in preclinical studies, a more general workflow has been proposed, starting with the construction of a comprehensive network and aiming to understand the molecular mechanisms in different human diseases (not only in cancer), to predict drug sensitivity and to identify optimal therapeutic approaches.
- The **Covid-19 DM** is the result of a remarkable community effort that brought together 277 scientists from 130 institutions around the world. Applications: using several systems biology tools and omics data, Niarakis et al. leveraged the Covid-19 DM to unravel certain biological mechanisms and signaling events following infection by SARS-CoV-2. Their pipelines make it possible to test combinatorial therapies and evaluate the repurposing of existing drugs to combat new waves of Covid-19 or other pandemics.

224

225 **Highlight Box.** The DM community is working together on several projects for which some maps have
226 already been successfully exploited: the Parkinson's DM (Fujita et al., 2014); the Atlas of Cancer Signalling
227 Network and applications (Kuperstein et al., 2015; Jdey et al., 2017; Monraz Gomez et al., 2019); the Covid-
228 19 DM and applications (Ostaszewski et al., 2021; Niarakis et al., 2023).

229

230 Foundation of multi-layered data structures

231 In ONTOX, PMs will constitute the foundation of multi-layer frameworks integrating physiology,
232 AOPs and AOP networks (e.g., van Ertvelde et al., 2023; Barnes et al., 2024; Verhoeven et
233 al., 2024), chemical and kinetic data. These frameworks will address the following adverse
234 outcomes: liver steatosis, cholestasis, tubular necrosis, crystallopathy, neural tube closure
235 and cognitive function defects. Enabling integration, annotation, and visualization of diverse
236 types of data, these multi-layered structures will enhance understanding of organ- and
237 disease-specific pathways in response to chemical perturbations.

238 Visualizing and analyzing your own data

239 PMs consist of a user-friendly and standardized visualization that allows for analyzing your
240 own datasets (e.g., omics). Using PMs, you can, for example, identify biological mechanisms
241 driving a pathology and uncover potential drug targets. Indeed, using the features of the
242 MINERVA platform, you can query external ontologies to identify chemicals and drugs that
243 interact with the molecular targets within the maps. More information on the current capabilities
244 of the platform for data visualization and analysis can be found in Mazein *et al.*, 2023.

245 **Improving *in vitro* and *in silico* risk assessment approaches**

246 While PMs will be integrated with AOPs and will be used to identify key molecules and
247 pathways involved in specific functions or diseases, they will support the development of
248 *in vitro* test batteries, advancing animal-free approaches for next-generation risk assessment.
249 Furthermore, PMs will aid in the development of quantitative methods for computational
250 disease modeling and for assessing chemical safety from perturbation of the biology.
251 Standardized PMs, AOPs and multi-layer frameworks can indeed be leveraged to predict the
252 toxicity of chemicals using data-driven (machine learning) and knowledge-driven *in silico*
253 models, with the goal of developing probabilistic risk assessment approaches that account for
254 the complex interactions between different physiological systems in the body.

255 **Education material**

256 PMs provide a visual representation of biological pathways and interactions that can serve as
257 educational material for training in physiology, toxicology and related disciplines. The user-
258 friendly interface of the MINERVA platform, the structure co-designed with domain experts,
259 the graphical standards and the comprehensive annotations undoubtedly facilitate the
260 exploration and understanding of the biological processes.
261

262 **4. Perspectives**

263 PMs can be defined as comprehensive graphical representations of biological processes and
264 interactions using the SBGN. The PMs developed within the ONTOX project are designed to
265 map the functional processes in the liver, kidney, and developing brain. This workflow,
266 however, can be adapted to map any physiological process. While the structure and
267 annotation scheme of PMs are expected to benefit the scientific community in terms of data
268 management, accessibility and interoperability, curation guidelines for PMs have been
269 developed, including a comprehensive description of the mandatory and recommended
270 annotations for each map feature in ONTOX. The capability of creating submaps (modules of
271 the full map) facilitates the integration of new data and updates, as well as the identification of
272 data gaps, prioritizing research needs, and enhancing the PMs' usability and scalability. The
273 modularized architecture of PMs also enables a more detailed and comprehensive mapping
274 of AOPs and key events, which can foster the development of novel *in vitro* assays for
275 assessing chemical toxicity. In addition, the use of annotations and controlled vocabularies to
276 establish linkages allows for connections between different communities and initiatives. PMs
277 are tools that need to be constantly updated, which is only possible through a collaborative,
278 community-based effort, drawing on the expertise and knowledge of biocurators and experts
279 from different fields. In particular, the ONTOX project aims to bring the toxicology and systems
280 biology communities closer together to create standardized and comprehensive PMs that will
281 play a crucial role in the development of NAMs for toxicological mechanistic next-generation
282 risk assessment.

283 **Data availability**

284 All the maps are available on our GitHub page⁵, on the BioStudies ONTOX database⁶, and on
285 the ONTOX MINERVA platform⁷, under the License Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
286 International (CC BY 4.0) License⁸.

287 **Acknowledgements**

288 The online browsing is supported by the MINERVA team⁹ at the Bioinformatics Core of the
289 Luxembourg Centre for Systems Biomedicine within the ELIXIR-LU framework¹⁰.

290 **Funding**

291 This work has received fundings from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and
292 innovation programme under grant agreement N° 963845 (ONTOX) and from the European
293 Research Council under the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework programme
294 (INSTant CARMA, grant agreement N° 101088919).

295 **Competing interests**

296 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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